

Compound D and E eluted by benzene-ethyl acetate (3:7) were separated and purified by repeated column chromatography on polyamide using water-methanol as the eluent.

Compound D: It was crystallised from methanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 185-86°. It was analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{11}$, gave green ferric reaction, orange-red Shinoda test and positive Molisch test. The uv spectra of the compound, λ_{max} (MeOH) 253 and 370 nm, showed it to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis with 6% sulphuric acid gave an aglycone, which was identified as quercetin by chromatographic and spectral comparison with an authentic sample. The aqueous part on working up for sugar showed the presence of rhamnose by co-pc with authentic rhamnose on Whatman No. 1 (butanol-acetic acid-water, 4:1:5 organic layer, R_f 0.33; butanol-ethanol-water, 4:1:2.2, R_f 0.36). Aniline hydrogen phthalate was used as the spraying reagent and the spots were developed by heating at $\sim 110^\circ$. Thus compound D is a monorhamnoside of quercetin. Hydrolysis of permethylated glycoside gave quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether which with $AlCl_3$ showed a bathochromic shift from 361 to 420 nm, thereby indicating that the rhamnose moiety was present at the 3-position⁵. Thus compound D was identified as quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside (quercitrin).

Compound E: It was crystallised as yellow needle-shaped clusters, m.p. 235-36°, analysed for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12} \cdot H_2O$. It gave an olive green colouration with $FeCl_3$, orange-red Shinoda test and a positive Molisch test. Its uv spectrum showed maxima at 254 and 370 nm indicating the compound to be a flavonol glycoside. On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone which was identified as quercetin and the sugar was identified as glucose by co-pc. Thus the compound is a mono-glucoside of quercetin. The pmr spectrum of its acetate taken in $CDCl_3$ showed signals due to four phenolic acetyls at τ 7.57 (3H), and 7.69 (9H), and four alcoholic acetyls at 7.87 (6H), 8.04 (3H) and 8.12 (3H). The signals over the range 4.4-6.2 account for the seven protons of the glucosyl residue. One of these, a doublet centred at 4.87 was assigned to the $C_{1''}$ proton, the large coupling constant (J 7 Hz) due to *trans*-diaxial with the $C_{2''}$ proton indicated the presence of β -configuration. The A-ring protons at 6- and 8-positions appeared as doublets at 3.3 (J 2.5 Hz) and 2.79 (J 2.5 Hz), respectively. The B-ring protons formed an ABX pattern characteristic of 3', 4'-oxygenated flavonoids. The 2'-proton showed up as a doublet at 1.98 (J 2.5 Hz), while 5'- and 6'-protons appeared as doublet at 2.7 (J 9 Hz) and quartet at 2.12 (J 2.5 Hz and 9 Hz), respectively. Compound E was thus characterised as quercetin 3-O- β -D-glucoside.

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Direct Determination of Mercury in Complex Compounds

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MERCURY(II) has been maximum cation deformability among the metal ions of the same group in the periodic table. Thus it is not surprising to find more organic ligands forming thermally stable chelates with mercury(II) in comparison to Zn^{2+} or Cd^{2+} . Mercury(II) has been determined using precipitants containing nitrogen and oxygen^{1,2}. Among those reagents benzoylacetoacetanilide and benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide need special mention. Those are not effective for the direct determination of mercury(II) from its coordinated compounds. The reagent acetylaceto-thioacetanilide, used in the present investigation easily precipitates HgS from the solutions of simple or chelated compounds of mercury. No drastic degradation³ of mercury chelates is necessary. HgS is very stable. Hence, if discarded as such, it will not pollute the atmosphere. Use of thioamide requires the hydrolysis of the reagent either in alkaline or acidic solutions (Willgerodt reaction⁴) for the homogenous precipitation of HgS . Moreover, simple thioamides cannot precipitate HgS from the experimental solution containing chelated Hg^{2+} ion. In some cases thioanilide forms complexes⁵ without giving sulphide ion. Hence in this report, acetylaceto-thioacetanilide (AATA) has been suggested as a HgS -precipitating agent.

Experimental

Acetylaceto-thioacetanilide [$CH_3CO.CH(CH_3-CO).CS.NH.C_6H_5$]: This reagent was prepared in the laboratory following the reported method⁶. Equimolar phenylisothiocyanate was mixed with sodium salt of acetylacetone. When the reaction was complete, the product was extracted with cold water and acidified. The solid thus separated was

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY(II)

Complex	Hg ^{II}	Weight of	Hg ^{II}	Relative error (%)	
	taken mg	HgS mg	found mg		
	154.5	179.14	153.6, 153.7	-0.58	-0.51
	146.3	158.04	146.3, 146.3	nil	nil
	118.2	137.05	118.2, 118.2	nil	nil
Complex					
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(BHAH)Hg(Ph).OH.Hg.C ₆ H ₅]NO ₃ ^a	100	110.96	100.10, 100.01	0.10,	0.01
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Pic HAH)Hg.C ₆ H ₅]NO ₃ ^a	100	110.96	100.08, 99.97	0.08,	-0.03
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Pic HA)Hg.C ₆ H ₅] ^a	100	110.96	99.95, 100.03	-0.05,	0.03
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Quin HA)Hg.C ₆ H ₅] ^a	100	110.96	100.00, 100.14	nil,	0.04
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Pic)] ^b	100	110.96	100.00, 99.94	nil,	-0.06
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Quin)] ^b	100	110.96	100.00, 100.09	0.12,	0.09
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Nic)] ^b	100	110.96	99.93, 100.02	-0.07,	0.02
[C ₆ H ₅ HgOH.HgC ₆ H ₅]NO ₃ ^c	100	110.96	100.08, 100.13	0.08,	0.13
[C ₆ H ₅ Hg(Bz)Hg.C ₆ H ₅]NO ₃ ^c	100	110.96	100.01, 99.95	0.01,	-0.05
[Hg(Phthelazinylformazan) ₂] ^d	100	110.96	100.06, 100.11	0.06,	0.11

^aRef. 8. ^bRef. 9. ^cRef. 10. ^dRef. 11.

filtered and dried, m.p. 104°. A 1.5% solution of the reagent in 50-60% aqueous ethanol was freshly prepared for each determination.

Mercury(II) solution : Mercuric chloride (G.R., E. Merck) was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide⁷ solution. The mercury content was found to be 130 mg per 10 ml of solution.

Apparatus : A E.C.L. electrical digital pH meter was used to record the acidity of the solutions.

Procedure : The stock solution of Hg^{II} nitrate was diluted to 150 ml containing 130 mg of the metal and the pH was adjusted to 3.5 using dilute nitric acid. The reagent solution containing 0.16-0.20 g of the reagent in aqueous ethanol was added dropwise with constant stirring. The mixture was left on a water-bath (~80°) for 15-20 min. It was then filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G₄) and washed with hot water (70-80°). The metal content was determined after drying the HgS using the conversion factor 0.8624. The results are consolidated in the Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The mercury(II) content of a solution could be determined in the presence of various metal ions (one fold excess) without any masking agents. The precipitated Hg may be washed successively with dilute nitric acid and acetone before drying.

Effect of pH : A set of experiments was carried out under identical conditions using 136.3 mg Hg^{II} but varying pH. The experimental results showed that the pH range 3.5-6.0 is very effective for quantitative precipitation process.

Effect of concentration of reagent and sequestering agents : Slight excess of reagent was needed for the complete precipitation of mercury(II). Na-K-

tartrate and Na₂-EDTA did not hinder the precipitation of mercury(II). Thus Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Bi^{III}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, V^V, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Sb^{III} did not interfere the determination. Use of Na₂-EDTA masked the interference of the foreign ions if present in large excess (five fold), particularly Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Bi^{III} and Sb^{III}.

Analysis for mercury(II) in compound : The solution of Hg^{II} compounds, either in aqueous or nonaqueous medium could be used for precipitation of HgS using slight excess of ethanolic solution of the reagent. Thus the method removes the difficulty in the analysis of Hg^{II}, particularly for organomercury compounds⁸⁻¹¹. In case of insoluble sample, dissolution is necessary.

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